

Research Article

Development and validation of stability indicating method for simultaneous estimation of ofloxacin and prednisolone in pharmaceutical dosage form

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ABSTRACT

Objective: A simple, specific, and fast stability indicating reverse phase liquid chromatographic method was established for simultaneous determination of ofloxacin and prednisolone in pharmaceutical formulations. The High Performance Liquid Chromatography method has adequate separation of Ofloxacin and Prednisolone in its dosage form.

Methods: The separation was achieved by BDS Hypersil C₁₈, with mobile phase Phosphate Buffer (potassium dihydrogen phosphate) (pH 4): Methanol (30:70 v/v). The mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. Injection volume 20 µl and wavelength of detection used was 275 nm. The retention time for Ofloxacin and Prdnisolone were obtained as 3.327 min and 5.680 min, respectively.

Results: The linearity of proposed method was investigated in range of 3-9 µg/ml and 10-30 µg/ml for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone respectively. The precision data for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone were found to be 0.42% and 0.90% respectively. The accuracy of the present method was evaluated at 80%, 100% and 120%. The Accuracy data for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone were found to be 1.12-0.49% RSD and 0.67-0.53% RSD respectively. LOD value was found to be 0.014 for Ofloxacin and 0.0297 for Prednisolone. LOQ value was found to be 0.042 for Ofloxacin and 0.090 for Prednisolone.

Conclusions: The method was found to be accurate, precise, specific, sensitive and robust according to acceptance criteria of International Council on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. The method was resulted in good separation of both the analytes and degradation products with acceptable tailing and resolution. The peak purity index for both the analytes after all types of stress conditions was ≥ 0.9999 indicated a complete separation of both the analyte peaks from degradation products. The developed method can be applied successfully for simultaneous determination of ofloxacin and prednisolone in pharmaceutical formulations and their stability studies.

Keywords: Reverse phase liquid chromatography, Ofloxacin, Prednisolone, Degradation products, ICH guidelines

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Introduction

Ofloxacin¹⁻³ [(*RS*)-7-fluoro-2-methyl-6-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-10-oxo-4-oxa-1-azatricyclo[7.3.1.0^{5,13}]trideca-5(13),6,8,11-tetraene-11-carboxylic acid] is an antibiotic used to treat certain infections caused by bacteria, such as pneumonia, bronchitis, venereal disease (VD), and prostate, skin, and urinary tract infections.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Ofloxacin.

Prednisolone⁴⁻⁶ [(11 β)-11,17,21-trihydroxypregna-1,4-diene-3,20-dione] is a synthetic glucocorticoid, a derivative of cortisol, which is used to treat a variety of inflammatory and autoimmune conditions. It is the active metabolite of the drug prednisone and is used especially in patients with liver failure, as these individuals are unable to metabolize prednisone into prednisolone.

Figure 2: Chemical structure of Prednisolone.

Combine this two drugs are used as an antibiotic to treat a variety of eye infections, including keratitis, pink eye, conjunctivitis, blepharitis, corneal ulcers, stye, uveitis and iritis.

From literature review, it has been revealed that very few method have been reported for Ofloxacin^{7,8} and Prednisolone^{9,10} as a single drug or in combination with other drugs hence, the

current study has been carried out with the aim to develop and validation of stability indicating reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the simultaneous estimation of ofloxacin and Prednisolone in pharmaceutical dosage form.

Materials and Methods

Chemical and solvents

Ofloxacin and Prednisolone were procured from suryen pharma as a gift sample. HPLC grade solvents: Water, Methanol, Acetonitrile were obtained from Merck India Ltd., Mumbai. Ocepred eye drop was purchased from SUN Pharmaceuticals, India.

HPLC instrument and chromatographic Conditions

Shimadzu 2320 made by Perkin Elmer, USA, Gradient system, Quaternary LC pump, Injector: Rheodyne injector (20 μ l capacity) and Detector: PDA detector.

Preparation of stock solution

A 10 mg of Ofloxacin was weighed and transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask. Volume was made up to the mark with mobile phase. Pipetted out 1.2 ml from that and transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask. Volume was made up to the mark with mobile phase.

A 10 mg of Prednisolone was weighed and transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask. Volume was made up to the mark with mobile phase. Pipetted out 4 ml from that and transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask. Volume was made up to the mark with mobile phase.

Preparation of sample solution

Take 1 ml from the Ofloxacin stock solution and 1 ml from Prednisolone stock solution and transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and volume made up to the mark by mobile phase which was used in particular trials.

Selection of detection wavelength

The sensitivity of HPLC method that uses UV detection depends upon proper selection of detection wavelength. An ideal wavelength is the one that gives good response for the drugs that are to be detected. In the present study drug solutions of Ofloxacin (12 ppm) and Prednisolone (40 ppm) were prepared in Methanol. These drug solutions were then scanned in UV region of 200-400 nm and overlay spectrums were recorded.

Figure 3: Overlay UV spectra of Ofloxacin and Prednisolone in methanol.

Selection of mobile phase

Based on sample solubility, stability, suitability and pKa various mobile phase compositions were tried to get a good resolution and sharp peaks. The standard solution containing mixture of two drugs, as well as individual drugs were run in various mobile phases containing different ratio of Acetonitrile, Methanol, Water and Phosphate buffer (potassium dihydrogen phosphate) of pH 4. The mobile phase containing Phosphate buffer (pH 4): methanol [30:70 v/v] proportion with detection wavelength 275 nm were selected.

Figure 4: Chromatogram of standard drugs of Ofloxacin and Prednisolone.

Table 1: Optimized chromatographic conditions for simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Prednisolone.

Parameters	Optimized Conditions
Instrument	Shimadzu LC-20 AT
Column	C18 (25 cm x 0.46 cm) Hypersil BDS
Mobile phase	Phosphate buffer (pH 4): methanol (30 : 70 v/v)
Flow rate	1.0 ml/min
Detection	275 nm
Injection volume	20 µl
Temperature	Ambient

Method validation

Validation of the optimized RP-HPLC method was carried out with respect to the following parameters.

Linearity

The linearity for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone were assessed by analysis of combined standard solution in range of 3-9 µg/ml and 10-30 µg/ml respectively, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 1.25, 1.5 ml solutions were pipette out from the Stock solution of Ofloxacin (120 µg/ml) and Prednisolone (400 µg/ml) and transfer to 100 ml volumetric flask and make up with mobile phase to obtain 3, 4.5, 6, 7.5, 9 µg/ml, and 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 µg/ml for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone respectively. In term of slope, intercept and correlation co-efficient value. The graph of peak area obtained verses respective concentration was plotted. Correlation co-efficient for calibration curve Ofloxacin and Prednisolone was found to be 0.993 and 0.998 respectively.

The regression line equation for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone are as following:

For Ofloxacin $y = 106.8x - 32.19$ and Prednisolone: $y = 76.16x - 38.14$.

Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was calculated by recovery studies. It is carried out by preparing

the samples at the level of 80%, 100% and 120% of target concentration. The samples were prepared in triplicate for each level. The results of studies along with its evaluation are given in Table 4 and 5.

Precision

a) Repeatability

The precision of the method was checked by repeated scanning and measurement of the area of solutions (n = 6) of The data for repeatability of peak area measurement for Prednisolone (20 µg/ml) and Ofloxacin (6µg/ml) based on six measurements of same solution of Prednisolone (20 µg/ml) and Ofloxacin (6 µg/ml). The % RSD for Prednisolone and Ofloxacin was found to be 0.90 and 0.42 respectively.

b) Intermediate precision (reproducibility)

The intra-day and inter-day precisions of the developed method was determined by analyzing corresponding responses in triplicate on the same day and on 3 different days over a period of 1 week for 3 different concentrations of standard solutions of Ofloxacin (3, 6 and 9 µg/ml) and of Prednisolone (10, 20, 30 µg/ml). Results were reported in terms of % RSD. The % RSD value for intraday is 0.62 and 0.87 for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone respectively. The % RSD value for interday is 0.72 and 0.81 for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone respectively. (Table 7 and 8).

Limit of detection and Limit of quantitation

Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantitation (LOQ) for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone were determined (Table 9) by calibration curve method. Peak area of analysis was plotted against concentration.

Robustness

The robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage. Robustness of the method was investigated under a variety of

conditions including changes of pH of mobile phase, flow rate (Table 10).

Quantitative estimation of pharmaceutical dosage form

Assay of eye drop was done by following method. Preparation of standard stock solution by taking 6 mg Ofloxacin and 20 mg Prednisolone and make up to 100 ml separately, took 1 ml from both the solution ofloxacin (60 ppm) and Prednisolone (200 ppm) and make up to 10 ml. Take sample solution equivalent to 6 mg Ofloxacin and make up to 10 ml (Table 11).

Results and Discussion

The results of method development and validation studies on simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Prednisolone in the current study involving phosphate buffer (pH-4): methanol (30:70 v/v) as the mobile phase for RP-HPLC is given below.

Table 2: Calibration curve data of Ofloxacin.

Sr.No	Concentration (µg/ml)	Area
1	3	307.61
2	4.5	414.49
3	6	622.85
4	7.5	766.71
5	9	932.89

Figure 5: Calibration curve of Ofloxacin.

Table 3: Calibration curve of Prednisolone.

Sr.No	Concentration (µg/ml)	Area
1	10	737.485
2	15	1090.495
3	20	1492.054
4	25	1838.463
5	30	2267.736

Figure 6: Calibration curve of Prednisolone.

Table 4: Recovery data of Ofloxacin for the developed method.

Concentration of Sample Taken (µg/ml)	Concentration of Pure API spiked (µg/ml)	Mean Total Concentration Found (n=3) (µg/ml)	%Recovery Mean (n=3)	%RSD
3	2	2.011	100.1	1.12
3	3	3.022	99.78	0.65
3	4	3.957	99.79	0.49

Table 5: Recovery data of Prednisolone.

Concentration of Sample Taken (µg/ml)	Concentration of Pure API spiked (µg/ml)	Mean Total Concentration Found (n=3) (µg/ml)	%Recovery Mean (n=3)	%RSD
10	8	7.2	99.85	0.76
10	10	9.48	99.61	0.5
10	12	11.96	99.7	0.53

Table 6: Repeatability data of Ofloxacin and Prednisolone.

Concentration	Ofloxacin (6 µg/ml)	Prednisolone (20 µg/ml)
Area	620.138	1486.372
	621.375	1458.613
	615.927	1492.32
	623.849	1495.324
	620.759	1487.859
	621.998	1490.828
Mean	620.67	1485.219

±SD	2.65	13.41
%RSD	0.427	0.903

Table 7: Intra-day and inter-day precision data of Ofloxacin.

Concentration (µg/ml)	Intra-Day Area Mean (n=3) ±SD	%RSD	Inter-Day Area Mean (n=3) ±SD	%RSD
3	305.60 ± 2.75	0.90	305.19 ± 2.71	0.88
6	618.08 ± 4.21	0.68	616.84 ± 3.11	0.50
9	926.52 ± 5.75	0.62	924.49 ± 6.74	0.72

Table 8: Intra-day and inter-day precision data of Prednisolone.

Concentration (µg/ml)	Intra-Day Area Mean (n=3) ±SD	%RSD	Inter-Day Area Mean (n=3) ±SD	%RSD
10	726.04 ± 13.47	1.85	727.85 ± 8.87	1.22
20	1476.57 ± 16.15	1.09	1474.7 ± 14.88	1.00
30	2216.87 ± 19.47	0.87	2213.8 ± 18.11	0.81

Table 9: Regression analysis data and summary of validation parameter.

Parameters	RP-HPLC method	
	Ofloxacin	Prednisolone
Linearity (µg/ml)	3-9	10-30
Slope	106.8	76.16
Intercept	32.19	38.14
Correlation coefficient	0.993	0.998
LOD (µg/ml)	0.014	0.029
LOQ (µg/ml)	0.042	0.09

Table 10: Result of robustness study of Ofloxacin and Prednisolone.

Factor	Level	Ofloxacin		Prednisolone	
pH of mobile phase (±0.2)	l	Peak area	RS D	Peak area	RS D
3.8	3.8	635.4	1.18	1524.0	1.31
	8			5	
	4.0	605.2		1484.3	
4.2	3			6	
	4.2	593.0		1418.1	
Flow rate (ml/min) (±0.2)	0.8	643.9	1.23	1537.6	1.23
	7			3	
	1.0	605.2		1484.3	
3				6	
	1.2	606.3		1444.9	
3				0	

Table 11: Statistical evaluation of eye drop analysis.

Parameters	OCEPRED Eye Drop	
	Ofloxacin	Prednisolone
Amount present	0.3% w/v	1.0% w/v
Amount found	2.8 mg	9.98 mg
%Purity	97.87	98.89
%RSD*	1.13	1.22
Limit	98%-102%	95%-105%

*denotes average of six determination

Table 12: Sensitivity and system suitability parameters.

Parameters	Ofloxacin	Prednisolone
Theoretical plates	7038	4468
Retention time (min)	3.327	5.680
Tailing factor	1.364	1.636
Resolution	9.442	

Force degradation studies¹¹

Acid degradation studies

Ofloxacin and Prednisolone were found to undergo acid degradation very rapidly. The reaction in 0.1N HCL in 1 h showed extensive

degradation for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone with additional peaks. % Degradation for Ofloxacin was about 27.3% at 0.1 N HCL (1 h). % Degradation of Prednisolone was about 21.1% at 0.1 N HCL (1 h). So, Ofloxacin and Prednisolone are acid labile in nature.

Figure 7: Chromatogram of combined Ofloxacin and Prednisolone standard mixture in acid degradation (0.1 N HCL, 1 h).

Base degradation study

Ofloxacin and Prednisolone were found to undergo base degradation very rapidly. The reaction in 0.1 N NaOH for 60 min. showed extensive degradation for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone with additional peaks. % degradation was higher in 0.1 N NaOH. % Degradation for Ofloxacin was about 32.5 % at 0.1 N NaOH (1 h). % Degradation for Prednisolone was about 23.7% at 0.1 N NaOH (1 h). So, Ofloxacin and Prednisolone are basic labile in nature.

Figure 8: Chromatogram of combined Ofloxacin and Prednisolone standard mixture in base degradation (0.1 N NaOH, 1 h).

Oxidative degradation studies

The reaction with 3% hydrogen peroxide showed degradation for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone with additional peaks. % Degradation was higher in 3% hydrogen peroxide. % Degradation for Ofloxacin was about 22.7% at 1 h. % Degradation for Prednisolone was about 16.4% at 1 h. So,

ofloxacin and Prednisolone are labile in nature for hydrogen peroxide.

Figure 10: Chromatogram of combined Ofloxacin and Prednisolone standard mixture in oxidative degradation (3% H₂O₂, 1 h).

Thermal degradation studies

Ofloxacin was found to undergo thermal degradation very rapidly. The reaction with 105 °C for 30 min showed extensive degradation for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone with additional peaks. % Degradation was higher in 105 °C. % Degradation for Ofloxacin was about 34.9% at 1 hour. % Degradation for Prednisolone was about 20.7% at 1 h. So, Ofloxacin and Prednisolone are labile nature in thermal condition.

Figure 11: Chromatogram of combined Ofloxacin and Prednisolone standard mixture in thermal degradation (105 °C, 30 min).

Photo degradation studies

Ofloxacin and Prednisolone were found to undergo sunlight degradation very rapidly. The reaction for 2 h showed extensive degradation for Ofloxacin and Prednisolone with additional peaks. % Degradation for Ofloxacin was about 10.7% at 1 h and 21.6 at 2 h. % Degradation for Prednisolone was about 17.7% at 1 h and 25.4 at 2 h. So, ofloxacin and Prednisolone are labile nature in sunlight condition.

Figure 12: Chromatogram of combined tablet mixture in sunlight degradation (2 h).

Table 13: Results of forced degradation study of ofloxacin.

Stress Conditions	Time (min)	Retention Time (min)	Area	% Area	Degradants (% area)
0.1 N HCl	60	3.300	458.651	72.4	27.6
	60	3.283	478.158	67.5	32.5
0.1 N NaOH	60	3.307	498.519	77.2	22.8
	30	3.283	463.163	65.1	34.9
3% H ₂ O ₂	60	3.68	3.287	89.3	10.7
	120	3.77	4.157	78.4	21.6
Heat exposure	60	3.283	463.163	65.1	34.9
	30	3.283	463.163	65.1	34.9
Sunlight	60	3.68	3.287	89.3	10.7
	120	3.77	4.157	78.4	21.6

Table 14: Results of forced degradation study of Prednisolone.

Stress Conditions	Time (min)	Retention Time (min)	Area	% Area	Degradants (% area)
0.1 N HCl	60	5.750	1403.33	78.9	21.1
	60	5.680	1344.32	76.3	23.7
0.1 N NaOH	60	5.760	1378.89	83.6	16.4
	30	5.730	1423.62	79.3	20.7
3% H ₂ O ₂	60	5.627	1125.2	82.3	17.7
	120	4.360	433.276	74.6	25.4
Heat exposure	60	5.730	1423.62	79.3	20.7
	30	5.730	1423.62	79.3	20.7
Sunlight	60	5.627	1125.2	82.3	17.7
	120	4.360	433.276	74.6	25.4

Conclusions

A simple, fast and accurate stability indicating RP-HPLC method is described for simultaneous determination of ofloxacin and prednisolone in pharmaceutical formulations. The developed method was validated by testing its linearity, accuracy, precision, limits of detection and quantitation and specificity. The method is simple, fast and is without the use of ion pair or any derivatization reagent. The method is good enough to separate the peaks of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) from the degradation products (produced during forced degradation studies). So, it is concluded that the method can be successfully used for any kind of stability and validation studies.

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